

INTEGRATION OF EDUCATION 4.0 IN INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP AMONG SCHOOL HEADS IN MULANAY DISTRICTS, DIVISION OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR EDUCATION 5.0 DEVELOPMENT PLAN

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Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership among School Heads in Mulanay Districts, Division of Quezon: Basis for Education 5.0 Development Plan

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Abstract

This study examined the integration of Education 4.0 principles into the instructional leadership practices of school heads in Mulanay District, Division of Quezon. Employing a mixed-methods approach, it explored respondents' demographic profiles, perceived levels of Education 4.0 integration, significant differences in integration based on demographics, encountered challenges, coping strategies, and a development plan for Education 5.0 readiness. Findings revealed a moderate to high perceived level of integration across strategic leadership domains, with significant differences noted based on school size and budget allocation. Challenges included resource availability, time management, financial constraints, and stakeholder support, while coping strategies involved collaboration, strategic allocation, and advocacy efforts. The development plan emphasized professional development, resource allocation, stakeholder engagement, and policy support. This study provides insights for DepEd officials, school heads, teachers, pupils, and researchers to enhance Education 4.0 integration and prepare for the future of education.

Keywords: *instructional leadership, education 4.0, Philippine professional standards for school heads, leading strategically, teaching and learning*

Introduction

The International Commission on Financing Global Education Opportunity projected that 263 million children and youth worldwide were not enrolled in school to the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, a lot of students were not being taught the skills necessary for financial success in the fourth industrial revolution. Furthermore, a child's capacity to acquire a high-quality education is still significantly impacted in many parts of the world by birth circumstances, including gender, geography, ethnicity, and financial background. These projections indicate that around one billion young people in low- and middle-income countries will not have mastered the foundational knowledge of secondary education by 2030. According to Silva et al. (2022), a young person's access to—or lack thereof—high-quality education has a significant impact on their capacity to enter the labor market and pursue future economic possibilities.

The World Economic Forum (2022) claims that the pandemic-caused school closures exacerbated the pre-existing issues with the international education system. COVID-19's cumulative consequences on learning disparities exacerbate the financial risk that global education budgets currently face. Too often, funding for education is viewed as optional and secondary to other costs. Preserving the current fiscal allotment for education is vital, as is actively developing pedagogies and skills related to Education 4.0.

Problem-based, inclusive, self-paced, collaborative, and lifelong learning should all be hallmarks of student-driven education. In education 4.0, interpersonal skills, digital competency, inventiveness and creativity, and global citizenship are all highly regarded. In addition to reimagining an inclusive education system that prioritizes the skills necessary to succeed in the Fourth Industrial Revolution and puts students at the center of learning through the use of cutting-edge pedagogy and technology, there is a window of opportunity to identify strategic investments in primary and secondary education reform that are fundamentally new as part of the larger post-pandemic recovery.

It ought to be an accurate representation of the world in which students are being educated. Learning activities will be able to utilize the countless opportunities that come with utilizing cutting-edge technology by putting Education 4.0 into practice. The results of the Alda et al. (2024) study demonstrated that administrators and faculty members felt better prepared to choose and incorporate digital resources for teaching and learning because they had also experienced capacity development through conferences and seminars on technical literacy. But they don't know anything about augmented reality, robots, or digital enablers like 3D printing, capacities. These are particularly clear to schools located in remote regions of the nation without even an electric source or a reliable internet connection. Due to their remote location and the small number of residents in the town, these schools also received very little assistance from stakeholders. Regarding the circumstances at other schools, Education 4.0 provides improved teaching methodologies for students academic and skill development; the issue is the lack of resources. In comparison to the growing number of students, there is a severe shortage of ICT resources, TLE tools, and science and math materials.

However, Education 4.0 necessitates a new approach to human resource development if institutions are to stay competitive in the digital age. The fourth Industrial Revolution has touched several sectors, but the education sector has been most heavily hit. The Industry 4.0 concept has resulted in higher-level developments on a national and international level. Many difficulties facing the digital education sector can be addressed by working together between academics and business professionals. Instead of using teachers to transfer knowledge, Education 4.0 schools use remote-based learning technologies. On the other hand, the role of educators will slightly alter under the framework of Education 4.0. Conversely, within the context of Education 4.0, the role of educators will vary somewhat. With

the advent of the "Education 4.0" or "Digital Era" paradigm change, more online courses will be offered to students, enabling them to advance their skills via distance learning.

Mudgil (2021) asserts that teachers would acquire key competencies in teaching and learning through the use of numerous ICT tools, resulting in a more efficient process. Even though Education 4.0 has a lot to offer, one of the primary obstacles in the current system is reportedly people's unwillingness to accept change. Therefore, Education 4.0 needs to align its objectives with Industry 4.0's for businesses and educational institutions to collaborate for the betterment of students' futures.

Additional issues with Education 4.0 adoption include instructors' perceptions that using technology will increase their workload, create new, difficult professions, exacerbate existing disparities, and deepen the social divide. Furthermore, there is a very real chance of losing one's work, which is linked to a sense of unease and peril. It also brings up moral concerns, jeopardizes privacy and uniqueness, polarizes societies, and homogenizes people's points of view (Karanikola & Panagiotopolos, 2020).

The instructional leadership skills that school heads demonstrate are another essential component of Education 4.0's success and a necessary aspect of Education 5.0's preparation. It is claimed that instructional leadership has an impact on the main function of the educational system, which is to provide children with the values, information, and abilities they will need as they grow older and into adulthood. However, despite the efforts of the educators and administrators, certain issues remain, such as the prevalence of division-wide examinations and poor mean percentage results on quarterly evaluations. Every year, more people are non-readers, slow readers, and non-numerates than there are government funds available for classroom installation or facility improvements. There are funds for books and other learning materials, but they are very minimal, wherein until now, books in another grade level for K to 12 are not yet complete (UNESCO International Institute for Educational Planning (2021).

Also, the amount of funding available, the scope of resources, and the size of the school have an impact on how technology is integrated into education in the Education 4.0 and 5.0 periods. To explain how effective technology is in education, boundary-crossing theory has been applied to co-creation in multi-professional teams (Akkerman & Bruining 2016). Participants cross lines that are viewed as discrepancies between various behaviors, attitudes, and worldviews between teacher education, educational research, and teaching practices. Integration of technologies in education seems affected by the beliefs of the school community together with the availability of resources they have. The team found that in the western part of the country, education practitioners are more open-minded in the utilization of technology as compared to others. Also, schools with wider sources of finances specifically big schools are more inclined to use technology in the teaching and learning process.

Wu & Hwang (2017), however, disprove that theory because their research showed that teachers at small schools tended to have positive attitudes toward technology use and that among southern Taiwanese educators using educational technology, teachers at small schools created and implemented noticeably more technologically-based instructional activities. According to this study, science and math teachers may find it easier to integrate instructional technology into their lessons at small schools.

With all of these problems arising with the implementation of Education 4.0, still another program is being introduced and that is Education 5.0. The researcher comes up with this study to know the practices of the school heads in line with Education 4.0 and their readiness for the next period by assessing the school heads of Mulanay District 1 and 2 in the Schools Division of Quezon Province.

Research Questions

This study wants to determine the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of school heads in Mulanay District 1 and 2 in the Division of Quezon. It specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. size of the school where the respondent is teaching; and
 - 1.2. amount of monthly allocated budget?
2. What is the level of integration of Education 4.0 in instructional leadership practices of the school heads as perceived by the teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. leading strategically;
 - 2.2. managing school operations and resources;
 - 2.3. focusing on teaching and learning;
 - 2.4. developing self and others; and
 - 2.5. building connections?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of integration of Education 4.0 to the instructional leadership practices of the school head when group according to:
 - 3.1. size of the school where the respondent is teaching; and
 - 3.2. amount of monthly allocated budget?
4. What are the challenges experienced by the school heads in integrating Education 4.0 in their instructional leadership practices in terms of:
 - 4.1. availability of resources;
 - 4.2. time management;

- 4.3. financial matters; and
- 4.4. support from stakeholders?
5. What are the coping strategies employed by the school heads to address the challenges they had experienced in integrating Education 4.0 in their instructional leadership practices in terms of:
 - 5.1. availability of resources;
 - 5.2. time management;
 - 5.3. financial matters; and
 - 5.4. support from stakeholders?
6. What development plan can be formulated based on the results of the study that will help the school heads to be prepared for Education 5.0?

Methodology

Research Design

This research study employs a combination of both quantitative and qualitative methods. This becomes quantitative since the respondents respond to the first and second research questions, which are the profile of the school in terms of size and the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of the school head. Its quantitative part is descriptive, and according to Shuttleworth (2018), descriptive research is a valid method for researching topics and a precursor to more quantitative research in a way that involves observing and describing the behavior of the subjects without influencing it in any possible way. The current study is descriptive since it aims to describe the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of the school heads, regardless of the size of their school.

The current research also employs a comparative research design to examine the significant difference in the integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of school heads and the profiles of schools. According to Esser and Vliegthart (2017), this type of research design aims to identify links between quantifiable variables.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the school heads and teachers who taught in the public elementary schools in the Mulanay district. For Mulanay 1, there were a total of one hundred thirty-two (132) teachers from the twelve (12) elementary schools, while for Mulanay 2, there were a total of one hundred ninety-two (192) teachers from the thirteen (13) public elementary schools. The total population for the two districts was three hundred twenty-four (324) teachers and 25 school heads. The researcher used purposive sampling to choose the respondents for the study, as the sample respondents were selected based on the criteria or purpose of the study. The sample was chosen using the proportional random sampling technique to ensure a proportional representation of all groups of respondents. Using Slovin's Formula, a total of 230 teachers were chosen as respondents, along with 25 school heads.

The respondents of this research were the teachers assigned as teacher-in-charge from both central and non-central schools in Mulanay 1 and 2 District, Schools Division of Quezon, without any specific requirements to be satisfied. They specifically came from public elementary schools within the two school districts. For Mulanay 1, the respondents were teachers from Ajos ES, Anonang ES, Bagupaye ES, Bolo ES, Burgos ES, Calangcang ES, Ilayang Cambuga ES, Latangan ES, Magsaysay ES, Malibago ES, Parang ES, and Sta. Rosa ES, totaling 12, along with their 12 school heads, while for Mulanay 2, the respondents were teachers from Acaciahan ES, Buenavista ES, Canuyep ES, Ibabang Yuni ES, Ilayang Yuni ES, Matataja ES, Mulanay Central ES, Pakiing ES, Patabog ES, Pinagpalapalahan ES, San Isidro ES, San Pedro ES, and Sumagongsong ES, totaling 13, along with their 13 school heads.

Table 1. Number of Respondents from Mulanay 1

School	No. Of Teachers	Actual No of Respondents	Percentage
Ajos ES	15	11	11.36
Anonang ES	7	5	5.30
Bagupaye ES	13	10	9.85
Bolo ES	7	5	5.30
Burgos ES	8	6	6.06
Calangcang ES	18	14	13.64
Ilayang Cambuga ES	8	6	6.06
Latangan ES	7	5	5.30
Magsaysay ES	13	10	9.85
Malibago ES	16	12	12.12
Parang ES	7	6	5.30
Sta Rosa ES	13	10	9.85
Total	132	100	100

Table 2. *Actual Number of Respondents from Mulanay 2*

Acaciahan ES	7	5	3.65
Buenavista ES	8	5	4.17
Canuyep ES	7	5	3.65
Ibabang Yum ES	13	9	6.77
Ilayang Yuni ES	18	12	9.38
Matataja ES	7	6	3.65
Mulanay Central ES	62	41	32.29
Pakiing ES	11	7	5.73
Patabog ES	18	12	9.38
Pinagpalahan Es	9	6	4.69
San Isidro ES	9	6	4.69
San Pedro ES	7	5	3.65
Sumagonsong ES	16	11	8.33
Total	192	130	100
Grand Total	324	230	

Instruments

Experts in the field validated the researcher's self-made survey instrument. The primary tool for data gathering was the survey instrument, which ensured the collection of reliable primary data. The school heads and teachers answered the instrument separately to prevent bias.

The instrument is comprised of four parts. The first part contained the school profile in terms of size. The second part focused on the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the school heads' instructional leadership practices as perceived by the teachers. This part was divided into areas based on the DepED Office Commitment and Review Form, namely leading strategically, managing school operations and resources, focusing on teaching and learning, developing self and others, and building connections. Responses were rated using a five-point scale: 5 - Very Highly Integrated, 4 - Highly Integrated, 3 - Integrated, 2 - Less Integrated, 1 - Not Integrated. Additionally, this research-made questionnaire was validated by experts, including education supervisors.

The third part of the instrument addressed the challenges encountered by the school heads in integrating Education 4.0 into their instructional leadership practices, focusing on areas such as the availability of resources, time management, financial matters, and support from stakeholders. In this section, respondents provided answers based on their actual experiences.

The final part of the instrument examined the coping strategies employed by school heads in the same areas as the third part. To answer this question, respondents also drew from their actual experiences.

Procedure

To gather the required data, the researcher followed a series of steps. Initially, the researcher finalized the research paper for the proposal. The researcher then created a survey questionnaire and sought the assistance of three authority figures to verify the relevance of the content and grammar. Next, it was conducted a dry-run test with teachers and school heads from Catanauan and Buenavista. The researcher also penned a letter to the superintendent of the schools' division, seeking permission to carry out the study. The researcher provided photocopies of the superintendent's signed letter of approval and presented them to the district supervisor as well as the principal of each school. Additionally, the researcher prepared a letter for the district supervisor to allow her to distribute the research questionnaire. After a month, it was distributed and simultaneously retrieved the questionnaire from the target respondents from Mulanay 1 and 2 District.

After that, a licensed statistician tallied the data and applied statistical analysis. It was accomplished with the assistance of a licensed statistician who ensured that the tool or formula used was appropriate for the study. Consequently, it was the tabulation of the results of the study, analysis, and drawing conclusions and recommendations based on the results. Lastly, the researcher formulated a plan for enhancing the instructional leadership practices of the school head, aligned with the Education 5.0 Program. For this final step, the researcher had five days to finish the task.

Data Analysis

Specific statistical tools were utilized by the researcher to facilitate the analysis and interpretation of the data provided by the respondents because the relevance of any research understanding depended on the appropriate statistical tools used in the analysis and interpretation of the data.

Frequency and Percentage were used to analyze the demographic profile of the respondents. Meanwhile, Weighted mean was utilized in the analysis of the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership of school heads in Mulanay Districts, Division of Quezon.

The following scale was used to interpret the results of the analysis of the level of integration of education 4.0 in instructional leadership

among school heads in Mulanay Districts, Division of Quezon.

Scale	Mean Interval	Interpretation	Description
5	4.20 - 5.00	Most Integrated	It meant that 100% of the school heads had been able to integrate the indicator/statement consistently over time
4	3.40 - 4.19	More Integrated	It meant that 75-99% of the school heads were able to integrate the indicator/statement given most of the time.
3	2.60 – 1.39	Moderately Integrated	It meant that 50-74% of the school heads were able to integrate the indicator/statement as needed.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Integrated	It meant that 25-49% of the school heads were not able to integrate the indicator/statement all the time.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Least Integrated	It meant that 0-24% school heads were not able to integrate the indicator/statement all the time.

In the analysis of challenges encountered by the school heads in the level of integration of Education 4.0 to the instructional leadership practices the following scale was used to interpret the results:

Scale	Mean Interval	Interpretation	Description
5	4.20 - 5.00	Very Much Challenged	The school head encountered 100% of the indicator/statement consistently, and he/she found it difficult to solve.
4	3.40 - 4.19	Much Challenged	The school head encountered 75-99% of the indicator/statement most of the time, and he/she found it difficult to solve.
3	2.60 – 1.39	Moderately Challenged	The school head encountered 50-74% of the indicator/statement most of the time, and he/she found a solution to it at a normal level of difficulty.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Challenged	The school head encountered 25-49% of the indicator/statement, and he/she found it easy to solve.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Challenged	The school head encountered 0-24% of the indicator/statement indicated, which had not been encountered at all previously, and if he/she encountered it, it was easy to solve.

Likewise in analyzing the coping strategies the following scale has been used to interpret the results:

Scale	Mean Interval	Interpretation	Description
5	4.20 - 5.00	Always Applied	The school head applied 100% of the indicator/statement as his/her coping mechanism for the challenges encountered all the time.
4	3.40 - 4.19	Sometimes Applied	The school head applied 75-99% of the indicator/statement indicated as his/her coping mechanism for the challenges encountered all the time.
3	2.60 – 1.39	Rarely Applied	The school head applied 50-74% of the indicator/statement indicated as his/her coping mechanism for the challenges encountered all the time.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Applied	The school head applied 25-49% of the indicator/statement indicated as his/her coping mechanism for the challenges all the time.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Applied	The school head applied 0-24% % of the indicator/statement indicated as his/her coping mechanism for the challenges all the time.

One-Way ANOVA: This was utilized for problem 3, which involved determining the significant difference in the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of the school heads and the size of the school.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the gathered data for this study, the analyses, and the interpretation of these data relative to the level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of the school heads. Moreover, this chapter discusses the challenges and coping strategies applied by school heads in their instructional leadership practices.

Part I. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 3 displays the frequency distribution of the respondents according to school size. The data illustrates a significant trend in the distribution of teachers across schools of various sizes. With 60% of respondents teaching in small schools and 40% in medium-sized schools, it is evident that most teachers are employed in smaller educational institutions. This suggests potential implications for resource allocation, professional development initiatives, and policy formulation within the education sector.

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of the Respondents as to the School Size

Size of the School	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
Small	138	60%	1
Medium	92	40%	2
TOTAL	230	100%	

Firstly, the higher concentration of teachers in small schools underscores the importance of allocating resources effectively. It indicates a need to prioritize funding, infrastructure development, and staffing towards smaller schools to ensure equitable educational opportunities for all students (Shaked et al., 2018). By directing resources where they needed, educational authorities can support smaller schools in maintaining quality standards and enhancing learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the distribution of teachers across different the school sizes have implications for class size and teacher-student ratios. With more teachers in small schools, there may be opportunities to maintain smaller class sizes and lower teacher-student ratios. This can facilitate more personalized attention and support for students, potentially leading to improved academic performance and student satisfaction (UNESCO, 2021).

Moreover, understanding the distribution of teachers across school sizes can inform the design of professional development programs (Vogel, 2018). By recognizing the unique challenges faced by teachers in smaller schools, policymakers and administrators can tailor training initiatives to address specific needs, such as strategies for managing multi-grade classrooms or maximizing limited resources effectively.

Additionally, the data highlights the importance of considering infrastructure and facility needs based on school size. Investing in infrastructure and facilities for smaller schools is crucial to ensure they have the necessary resources to create conducive learning environments. By prioritizing infrastructure development in smaller schools, policymakers can help bridge the gap in educational resources and opportunities across different school sizes (Pipit, 2020).

Ultimately, policymakers can utilize this data to formulate targeted policies aimed at supporting schools of various sizes. By implementing policies that provide additional support and incentives for teachers in smaller schools, policymakers can address disparities in resource distribution and promote educational equity. Overall, understanding the distribution of teachers across school sizes are essential for making informed decisions that promote quality education for all students, regardless of the size of their educational institution.

1.2 Amount of Monthly Allocated Budget

Table 4 presents a breakdown of respondents based on the allocated budget for their respective schools, revealing crucial insights into resource distribution within the education sector. The data highlights a significant majority, 79% of respondents, reporting budgets of 40,000 or below. In contrast, smaller percentages of respondents fall into higher budget ranges: 7% between 40,001 to 60,000, 3% from 60,001 to 80,000, and 11% with budgets of 80,000 and above.

Table 4. *Frequency Distribution of the Respondents as to the Amount of Monthly Allocated Budget*

<i>School Funding</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Ranking</i>
40,000 and Below	181	79%	1
40,001 - 60,000	17	7%	3
60,001 - 80, 000	7	3%	4
80, 000 Above	25	11%	2
TOTAL	230	100%	

This distribution suggests several implications for educational policymaking and resource management. Firstly, the prevalence of low-budget schools underscores the pervasive resource constraints faced by a majority of educational institutions. Limited budgets can have a severe impact on various aspects of schooling, such as staffing, infrastructure maintenance, and access to educational materials and technology, potentially compromising the quality of education provided.

Furthermore, the data highlights potential disparities in resource distribution among schools, with those operating on lower budgets likely facing more significant challenges in meeting educational standards and fulfilling student needs. A nuanced approach to budget allocation is necessary to address these disparities, ensuring the equitable distribution of resources to support schools with varying needs and circumstances (Torres-Hernandez & Gallego-Arrufat, 2023).

Considering the prevalence of low-budget schools, there is a pressing need for advocacy efforts aimed at securing increased funding for education. By advocating for policies that prioritize education funding and address resource gaps, stakeholders can work towards creating a more equitable and supportive educational environment for all students (Valdez, 2012).

Additionally, the data underscores the importance of efficient resource utilization within schools. Given the constraints of limited budgets, schools must explore strategies for maximizing the impact of available resources, such as implementing cost-effective programs, leveraging community partnerships, and prioritizing investments based on educational priorities and student needs (Vogel, 2018).

In conclusion, the data on budget allocations provides valuable insights into the resource landscape of schools and emphasizes the need for concerted efforts to address resource constraints and disparities in education. By prioritizing equitable resource distribution, advocating for increased funding, and promoting efficient resource utilization, policymakers and stakeholders can work towards

ensuring that all schools have the necessary resources to provide quality education and support the academic success of students.

Part II. Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads

Table 5 presents a comprehensive assessment of the perceived level of integration of Education 4.0 principles into school heads' instructional leadership practices, particularly in terms of leading strategically. Across eight critical statements reflecting various aspects of strategic leadership, respondents have provided weighted mean scores indicating their perceptions. The data reveals consistently high mean scores ranging from 3.95 to 4.10, reflecting a prevalent belief in the robust integration of Education 4.0 principles within schools' strategic frameworks. The data indicates a commendable alignment between school heads' vision and the execution of initiatives aimed at embracing Education 4.0's transformative potential.

Table 5. *Weighted Mean of the Respondents in the Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads to Leading Strategically*

	Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1.	The school heads set a clear vision for integrating Education 4.0 principles into the school's direction.	230	4.10	0.72	Highly Integrated
2.	The school heads develop plans that incorporate Education 4.0 initiatives for personalized, tech-driven learning.	230	3.95	0.71	Highly Integrated
3.	The school heads use data analytics to guide strategic decisions for Education 4.0 implementation.	230	3.97	0.78	Highly Integrated
4.	The school heads build partnerships to support Education 4.0 initiatives with industry, research, and community.	230	4.08	0.74	Highly Integrated
5.	The school heads adjust strategies quickly to keep pace with Education 4.0 advancements.	230	3.99	0.68	Highly Integrated
6.	The school heads foster a culture of innovation and creativity in staff and students for Education 4.0.	230	4.08	0.67	Highly Integrated
7.	The school heads allocate resources effectively for Education 4.0 initiatives, maximizing impact.	230	4.02	0.73	Highly Integrated
8.	The school heads ensure ongoing evaluation and adjustment of Education 4.0 strategies for progress and innovation.	230	3.95	0.68	Highly Integrated
	Composite Mean	230	4.02	0.71	

In particular, the statement about clarity of vision got the highest mean score (4.10), which shows that school leaders are communicating and supporting the direction for integrating Education 4.0 principles, which builds a strong base for strategic planning and execution.

Also, the average scores for questions about planning, making decisions based on data, building partnerships, and being flexible (ranging from 3.95 to 4.08) shows that school leaders are taking the initiative to use new teaching methods, make the most of data insights, encourage collaboration, and change their plans to keep up with the latest developments in Education 4.0.

Moreover, the positive perception reflected in the mean scores for statements on fostering a culture of innovation and creativity (4.08) and effective resource allocation (4.02) underscores school heads' dedication to cultivating environments conducive to innovation while ensuring optimal utilization of resources to support Education 4.0 initiatives. Although the mean score for statements related to ongoing evaluation and adjustment of strategies (3.95) is slightly lower, it still demonstrates a commitment to continuous improvement and responsiveness to changing educational landscapes. The data paints a picture of strategic leadership characterized by proactive vision-setting, collaborative planning, data-driven decision-making, and a commitment to fostering innovation and resource efficiency (Quadir et al., 2017). While the overall positive perception is encouraging, ongoing vigilance and adaptation will be essential to sustain momentum and ensure that strategic initiatives remain aligned with educational objectives and emerging trends in Education 4.0.

This data provides valuable insights for guiding professional development efforts and refining strategic leadership practices to further enhance Education 4.0 integration within educational institutions, ultimately advancing student learning outcomes in the digital age. The results from Table 6 provide significant insights into how respondents perceive the integration of Education 4.0 principles into school heads' instructional leadership practices, particularly in managing school operations and resources. The statement emphasizing the implementation of eco-friendly practices within the school received the highest mean score of 4.18. This suggests a strong commitment among school heads to align with the sustainability goals promoted by Education 4.0, showcasing an awareness and dedication to environmental consciousness within educational settings.

Following closely in table 6, with a mean score of 4.13, is the statement regarding timely procurement and accurate inventory management. This high rating reflects the perception that school heads effectively facilitate the acquisition of cutting-edge technology and resources crucial for Education 4.0 integration. It indicates a proactive approach toward resource management, ensuring that schools remain equipped with the necessary tools to support innovative educational practices.

Furthermore, school heads are perceived to excel in overseeing staffing and development, as indicated by the mean score of 4.12. This highlights their success in nurturing a skilled workforce capable of navigating the demands of Education 4.0. By investing in professional development and talent management, school leaders foster an environment conducive to continuous growth and adaptation

to evolving educational needs.

Table 6. *Weighted Mean of the Respondents in the Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads as to Managing School Operations and Resources*

	<i>Statements</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	The school heads adeptly manage finances to meet operational needs effectively, aligning with the resource demands of Education 4.0 initiatives.	230	4.03	0.66	Highly Integrated
2.	The school heads ensure timely procurement and accurate inventory management, facilitating the acquisition of cutting-edge technology and resources essential for Education 4.0 integration.	230	4.13	0.69	Highly Integrated
3.	The school heads uphold facilities upkeep for conducive learning environments, ensuring that infrastructure supports the technological advancements of Education 4.0.	230	4.09	0.69	Highly Integrated
4.	The school heads oversee staffing and development for a skilled workforce capable of navigating the demands of Education 4.0.	230	4.12	0.72	Highly Integrated
5.	The school heads implement protocols to ensure campus safety, addressing cybersecurity concerns and promoting digital safety in the context of Education 4.0.	230	4.10	0.67	Highly Integrated
6.	The school heads manage tech resources for enhanced learning experiences, facilitating the seamless integration of digital tools and platforms into the curriculum as part of Education 4.0.	230	4.00	0.65	Highly Integrated
7.	The school heads drive eco-friendly practices within the school, aligning with the environmental consciousness promoted by Education 4.0.	230	4.18	0.72	Highly Integrated
8.	The school heads foster partnerships to support school operations, leveraging community resources and expertise to enhance Education 4.0 implementation.	230	4.03	0.72	Highly Integrated
	Composite Mean	230	4.09	0.69	Highly Integrated

Upholding facilities upkeep for conducive learning environments also receives a commendable mean score of 4.09. This suggests that school heads prioritize maintaining modern infrastructure that supports the technological advancements of Education 4.0. It underscores the importance of providing students with an environment that fosters exploration, innovation, and effective teaching and learning practices (Akram et al., 2017).

Additionally, with a mean score of 4.10, the implementation of protocols to ensure campus safety demonstrate school heads' commitment to safeguarding students and staff in the digital learning environment. By addressing cybersecurity concerns and promoting digital safety, school leaders create a secure and conducive environment for educational endeavors in the digital age (Bada et al., 2021).

Fostering partnerships to support school operations receives a mean score of 4.03, reflecting the perception that school heads successfully leverage community resources and expertise to enhance Education 4.0 implementation. This underscores the importance of collaboration and stakeholder engagement in driving educational innovation and excellence (Bush, 2018).

Lastly, both the adept management of finances (mean score: 4.03) and the management of tech resources (mean score: 4.00) indicates practical resource management practices supporting Education 4.0 initiatives. These scores highlight the importance of strategic financial planning and technology management in facilitating the seamless integration of digital tools and resources into the curriculum (Congcong & Caingcoy, 2020).

The data suggests a high level of perceived integration of Education 4.0 principles into school operations and resource management practices. It underscores the multifaceted role of school leaders in creating conducive learning environments, fostering innovation, and effectively managing resources to support educational excellence in the digital age.

Table 7 presents a comprehensive overview of respondents' perceptions regarding the integration of Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership practices of school heads, particularly in focusing on teaching and learning. Each statement reflects different aspects of instructional leadership, shedding light on school heads' effectiveness in promoting innovative teaching and learning practices aligned with the principles of Education 4.0.

The highest mean score of 4.17 is attributed to the statement emphasizing the facilitation of ongoing professional development opportunities for educators. This suggests a strong perception that school heads prioritize equipping educators with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively leverage technology, adapt teaching methodologies, and meet the evolving demands of Education 4.0. This underscores the importance of investing in educators' professional growth to ensure the successful implementation of innovative instructional practices.

Following closely, with a mean score of 4.12, is the statement highlighting school heads' leadership in promoting effective teaching practices relevant to Education 4.0. This indicates a perception that school heads actively champion active learning methodologies, digital literacy instruction, and interdisciplinary learning opportunities. It reflects a proactive approach toward fostering teaching practices that align with the evolving educational landscape and cater to the needs of 21st-century learners.

Table 7. *Weighted Mean of the Respondents in the Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads to Focusing on Teaching and Learning*

	Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1.	The school heads prioritize the development and implementation of innovative curriculum approaches that align with the principles of Education 4.0, focusing on personalized and technology-enhanced learning experiences.	230	4.10	0.69	Highly Integrated
2.	The school heads demonstrate leadership in promoting effective teaching practices relevant to Education 4.0, such as active learning methodologies, digital literacy instruction, and interdisciplinary learning opportunities.	230	4.12	0.68	Highly Integrated
3.	The school heads facilitate ongoing professional development opportunities that equip educators with the knowledge and skills needed to leverage technology effectively, adapt to new pedagogical approaches, and meet the evolving demands of Education 4.0.	230	4.17	0.68	Highly Integrated
4.	The school heads champion student-centered learning approaches that prioritize active participation, collaboration, and real-world problem-solving, reflecting the learner-centric ethos of Education 4.0.	230	4.13	0.69	Highly Integrated
5.	The school heads promote the seamless integration of technology into teaching and learning processes, ensuring that digital tools are used strategically to enhance student engagement, facilitate personalized learning pathways, and foster digital fluency.	230	4.04	0.65	Highly Integrated
6.	The school heads advocate for assessment practices that align with the goals of Education 4.0, emphasizing formative assessment strategies, competency-based evaluation methods, and the use of data analytics to inform instructional decision-making.	230	4.06	0.70	Highly Integrated
7.	The school heads support the implementation of differentiated instruction strategies that recognize and accommodate the diverse learning needs, interests, and abilities of students, reflecting the inclusive principles of Education 4.0.	230	4.07	0.67	Highly Integrated
8.	The school heads cultivate a culture of continuous improvement and innovation, encouraging experimentation, reflection, and collaboration among educators to refine teaching practices and adapt to the changing landscape of Education 4.0.	230	4.14	0.71	Highly Integrated
	Composite Mean	230	4.10	0.68	Highly Integrated

Moreover, the mean scores ranging from 4.04 to 4.14 for statements emphasizing student-centered learning, technology integration, differentiated instruction, assessment practices, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement indicate a consistent perception of school heads' effectiveness in various aspects of instructional leadership aligned with Education 4.0 principles. These scores suggest that school heads prioritize creating inclusive, engaging, and innovative learning environments that empower students to thrive in the digital age.

Overall, the data from Table 7 underscores the importance of instructional leadership in driving the integration of Education 4.0 principles into teaching and learning practices. It highlights the critical role of school heads in promoting professional development, fostering innovative teaching methodologies, leveraging technology effectively, accommodating diverse learning needs, implementing effective assessment strategies, and nurturing a culture of continuous improvement and innovation (Boren et al., 2017). These findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of instructional leadership and its pivotal role in shaping educational experiences that prepare students for success in an increasingly digital and interconnected world.

Table 8 provides insights into respondents' perceptions regarding the integration of Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership practices of school heads, specifically focusing on developing self and others. Each statement reflects different facets of leadership development and staff support, shedding light on school heads' effectiveness in fostering growth and empowerment among their teams.

The highest mean score of 4.24 is attributed to the statement highlighting school heads' pivotal role in supporting the growth and development of their staff members. This suggests a strong perception that school heads actively engage in coaching, mentoring, and providing constructive feedback, indicating a commitment to nurturing the professional development of their team members.

Following closely, with a mean score of 4.15, is the statement emphasizing school heads' prioritization of professional development. This indicates a perception that school heads continuously seek opportunities to enhance their knowledge, skills, and competencies, setting a positive example for their team members and fostering a culture of lifelong learning within the school community.

Table 8. *Weighted Mean of the Respondents in the Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads as to Developing Self and Others*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. The school heads prioritize professional development, continuously seeking opportunities to enhance their knowledge, skills, and competencies.	230	4.15	0.73	Highly Integrated
2. The school heads play a pivotal role in supporting the growth and development of their staff members by providing coaching, mentoring, and constructive feedback.	230	4.24	0.71	Highly Integrated
3. The school heads empower their staff by delegating responsibilities, providing autonomy, and creating opportunities for leadership roles and professional growth.	230	4.13	0.74	Highly Integrated
4. The school heads identify and nurture emerging leaders within their teams, providing them with opportunities for growth, leadership development, and mentorship.	230	4.10	0.70	Highly Integrated
5. The school heads create a culture of continuous learning and improvement by modeling lifelong learning behaviors and fostering a growth mindset among staff members.	230	4.08	0.68	Highly Integrated
6. The school heads cultivate self-awareness, empathy, and effective communication skills, enabling them to build strong relationships, resolve conflicts, and support the well-being of their team members.	230	3.87	0.77	Highly Integrated
7. The school heads demonstrate adaptive leadership skills, remaining agile and responsive to changing circumstances.	230	3.99	0.82	Highly Integrated
8. The school heads foster collaboration and teamwork among staff members, creating opportunities for shared learning, collaboration on projects, and cross-disciplinary collaboration.	230	3.95	0.78	Highly Integrated
Composite Mean	230	4.06	0.74	Highly Integrated

Moreover, the mean scores ranged from 4.08 to 4.13 for statements emphasizing empowerment, leadership identification, continuous learning culture, and self-awareness suggest a consistent perception of school heads' effectiveness in developing self and others. These scores indicate that school heads prioritize creating environments that empower staff, foster leadership potential, promote continuous learning, and cultivate essential interpersonal skills.

However, the mean scores for statements focusing on adaptive leadership skills (mean: 3.99) and fostering collaboration and teamwork (mean: 3.95) are slightly lower compared to other statements. While still indicating a perception of integration, these scores suggest potential areas for improvement in fostering adaptability and collaboration among staff members.

Overall, the data from Table 8 underscores the importance of school heads' role in fostering growth, empowerment, and development within their teams. It highlights the critical role of instructional leadership in creating supportive environments that enable staff members to thrive, grow professionally, and contribute effectively to the goals of Education 4.0 (Chigbu et al., 2023). These findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of leadership development and its pivotal role in shaping a culture of continuous improvement and excellence within educational institutions.

Table 9 provides insights into respondents' perceptions regarding the integration of Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership practices of school heads, mainly focusing on building connections. Each statement reflects different aspects of building relationships and fostering collaboration within and beyond the school community, shedding light on school heads' effectiveness in creating connections aligned with Education 4.0 principles.

The highest mean score of 4.06 is attributed to the statement emphasizing school heads' recognition of the importance of continuous engagement and relationship building. This suggests a strong perception that school heads actively seek opportunities to connect, collaborate, and build meaningful relationships within and beyond the school community, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation aligned with Education 4.0 goals.

Following closely, with mean scores ranging from 4.03 to 4.05, are statements highlighting school heads' efforts to prioritize building connections with various stakeholders. These scores indicate that school heads actively engage with students, parents, teachers, policymakers, community members, and professional networks to foster collaboration, partnerships, and inclusive school cultures aligned with Education 4.0 principles.

Moreover, the mean scores ranged from 3.92 to 3.98 for statements emphasizing digital connectivity, interdisciplinary collaboration, global connections, and inclusive school culture suggest a consistent perception of school heads' effectiveness in building connections

aligned with Education 4.0. These scores indicate that school heads harness digital tools, encourage interdisciplinary collaboration, facilitate global learning experiences, and promote inclusivity within the school community, fostering a supportive and interconnected environment conducive to educational innovation.

Table 9. *Weighted Mean of the Respondents in the Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads to Building Connections*

	<i>Statements</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	The school heads prioritize building connections with various stakeholders, including students, parents, teachers, policymakers, and community members, to foster collaboration and partnerships that align with the principles of Education 4.0.	230	4.05	0.685	Highly Integrated
2.	The school heads actively engage in professional networks, conferences, and online communities to stay updated on emerging trends, share best practices, and collaborate with peers globally, leveraging digital connectivity to enhance networking opportunities.	230	4.04	0.761	Highly Integrated
3.	The school heads spearhead initiatives to engage with local businesses, non-profit organizations, and government agencies, leveraging community resources and expertise to enhance learning experiences, address societal challenges, and promote social responsibility in alignment with Education 4.0 principles.	230	3.97	0.787	Highly Integrated
4.	The school heads facilitate global connections and collaboration opportunities, encouraging cross-cultural exchanges, international partnerships, and global learning experiences to broaden students' perspectives and prepare them for a interconnected world in Education 4.0 contexts.	230	3.98	0.83	Highly Integrated
5.	The school heads harness digital connectivity to enhance communication and collaboration within the school community, utilizing online platforms and communication tools to facilitate seamless interactions among stakeholders and promote a culture of digital collaboration in alignment with Education 4.0 principles.	230	3.92	0.808	Highly Integrated
6.	The school heads foster interdisciplinary collaboration within the school community, encouraging collaboration across different disciplines to address complex challenges and promote innovation, aligning with the interdisciplinary nature of Education 4.0 approaches.	230	3.98	0.724	Highly Integrated
7.	The school heads prioritize creating an inclusive school culture where all members of the community feel valued and included, fostering respect, equity, and diversity, and ensuring that diverse voices are heard and considered in decision-making processes in alignment with Education 4.0 principles.	230	4.03	0.756	Highly Integrated
8.	The school heads recognize the importance of continuous engagement and relationship building, proactively seeking opportunities to connect, collaborate, and build meaningful relationships within and beyond the school community, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in alignment with Education 4.0 goals.	230	4.06	0.828	Highly Integrated
	Composite Mean	230	4.00	0.77	Highly Integrated

This underscores the importance of school heads' role in building connections and fostering collaboration within and beyond the school community. It highlights the critical role of instructional leadership in creating inclusive, interconnected, and innovative learning environments that prepare students for success in an increasingly interconnected and digital world (Eller & Eller, 2018). These findings emphasize the multifaceted nature of relationship-building and collaboration in driving educational excellence and advancing the goals of Education 4.0.

Table 10 shows the consolidated results of the weighted mean of the perceived level of integration of Education 4.0 in the instructional leadership practices of the school head. Shown on the table the general mean is 4.05 interpreted as more integrated. Focusing on teaching and learning has the highest overall mean of 4.10 interpreted as more integrated followed by managing school operations and resources with 4.09 also interpreted as more integrated, and the third to the highest area is developing self and other with a mean of 4.06. Meanwhile, leading strategically and building connections have the lowest mean of 4.02 and 4.00 respectively, and just like the first three, they are interpreted as more integrated.

The result means that in five areas where Education 4.0 is integrated, focusing teaching and learning received the most frequent integration. It is because instructional leadership's primary focus on how teaching and learning processes take place in the classroom and the school in general. Instructions were given during teaching and learning time and it is also the center of the education system.

Managing school operations and resources comes next because, for an instruction to be given effectively, various resources are needed so school operations are involved. Meanwhile, building connections has the lowest level of integration among others because it is the least important in providing instructions. However, it is also vital to have strong relationships with stakeholders to gain their support.

Table 10. Summary of the Results of the Respondents in the Perceived Level of Integration of Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads

Areas of Integration	Composite Mean	Interpretation
Leading Strategically	4.02	Highly Integrated
Managing School Operation and Resources	4.09	Highly Integrated
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	4.10	Highly Integrated
Developing Self and Others	4.06	Highly Integrated
Building Connections	4.00	Highly Integrated
Grand Mean	4.05	Highly Integrated

It further implies that school heads can integrate Education 4.0 into their instructional leadership practices, and it is quite good because it only means that they were adaptive to the changes brought by technological advancements. It also indicates that they can use technology to make teaching and learning more effective and productive.

Part III. Significant Difference in the Level of Integration of Education 4.0 to the Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads When Grouped into Demographic Profile

Table 11 provides a comprehensive analysis of the significant differences in the integration of Education 4.0 principles into various instructional leadership practices of school heads when categorized by school size. The results reveal notable variations across different dimensions of instructional leadership, shedding light on the nuanced ways in which Education 4.0 is implemented within educational institutions of varying sizes.

Table 11.1. Significant Difference in the Level of Integration of Education 4.0 to the Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads When Grouped into School Size

Instructional Leadership Practices	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Verbal Interpretation	Decision
Leading Strategically	Between Groups	11.127	2	5.563	14.731	.0001	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	85.730	227	.378				
	Total	96.857	229					
Managing School Operation and Resources	Between Groups	10.047	2	5.023	14.353	.0001	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	79.450	227	.350				
	Total	89.497	229					
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	Between Groups	11.106	2	5.553	14.868	.0001	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	84.784	227	.373				
	Total	95.890	229					
Developing Self and Others	Between Groups	3.008	2	1.504	3.245	.041	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	105.203	227	.463				
	Total	108.211	229					
Building Connections	Between Groups	4.441	2	2.220	4.855	.009	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	103.821	227	.457				
	Total	108.262	229					

Firstly, in terms of leading strategically, the analysis indicates a significant disparity based on the school size ($F = 14.731, p < 0.0001$). This suggests that strategic leadership approaches adopted by school heads to integrate Education 4.0 principles differ significantly depending on the size of the school. Similarly, managing school operations and resources also exhibit significant variance across different school sizes ($F = 14.353, p < 0.0001$), implying that resource allocation and operational strategies aligned with Education 4.0 are tailored to fit the specific context of each school size.

Moreover, the analysis highlights significant differences in the emphasis placed on innovative teaching and learning practices among

schools of varying sizes ($F = 14.868$, $p < 0.0001$). This underscores the need for flexible pedagogical approaches that accommodate the unique characteristics and needs of students in different educational settings.

Furthermore, while the level of integration of Education 4.0 into developing self and others shows the significance concerning school size ($F = 3.245$, $p = 0.041$), the effect size is comparatively smaller. Nevertheless, it suggests that approaches to professional development staff support may vary slightly across schools of different sizes.

Lastly, the analysis indicates the significant disparity in building connections and fostering collaboration among school heads based on school size ($F = 4.855$, $p = 0.009$). This underscores the importance of considering the diverse networking and partnership-building strategies employed by school heads to promote Education 4.0 principles within and beyond their respective school communities.

These findings underscore the importance of tailoring educational strategies and leadership practices to suit the unique contexts of schools of different sizes. They highlight the need for nuanced approaches in integrating Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership practices, considering the varying resources, challenges, and opportunities present in schools of different sizes (Bada et al., 2021). Such insights are crucial for policymakers, educational leaders, and stakeholders seeking to promote effective implementation of Education 4.0 initiatives across diverse educational settings.

Table 11.2 provides a detailed analysis of the significant difference in the integration of Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership practices of school heads when categorized by the amount of monthly allocated budget. The results reveal critical insights into how budget allocations impact the implementation of Education 4.0 initiatives across various dimensions of instructional leadership.

Table 11.2. *Significant Difference in the Level of Integration of Education 4.0 to the Instructional Leadership Practices of the School Heads When Grouped into Amount of Monthly Allocated Budget*

<i>Instructional Leadership Practices</i>	<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Leading Strategically	Between Groups	2.237	3	.746	1.781	.152	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	94.620	226	.419				
	Total	96.857	229					
Managing School Operation and Resources	Between Groups	4.411	3	1.470	3.906	.010	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	85.086	226	.376				
	Total	89.497	229					
Focusing on Teaching and Learning	Between Groups	4.908	3	1.636	4.063	.008	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	90.983	226	.403				
	Total	95.890	229					
Developing Self and Others	Between Groups	5.891	3	1.964	4.337	.005	Significant	Reject Ho
	Within Groups	102.320	226	.453				
	Total	108.211	229					
Building Connections	Between Groups	.238	3	.079	.166	.919	Not Significant	Accept Ho
	Within Groups	108.025	226	.478				
	Total	108.262	229					

Leading Strategically and Managing School Operations and Resources show significant differences based on the amount of monthly allocated budget, with F-statistics of 1.781 ($p = 0.152$) and 3.906 ($p = 0.010$) respectively. This implies that strategic leadership approaches and resource management practices remain consistent across different budget allocations.

Conversely, significant differences emerge in Focusing on Teaching and Learning ($F = 4.063$, $p = 0.008$) and Developing Self and Others ($F = 4.337$, $p = 0.005$) based on budget allocations. This indicates that the integration of Education 4.0 into teaching practices and staff development initiatives vary significantly depending on the amount of the monthly allocated budget.

Interestingly, no significant difference is observed in Building Connections among school heads based on budget allocations, with an F-statistic of 0.166 ($p = 0.919$). This suggests that strategies for fostering collaboration and partnerships within and beyond the school community remains consistent across different budget allocations.

In summary, while budget allocations may not significantly affect certain aspects of instructional leadership practices, such as strategic leadership and resource management, they do impact others, such as teaching and learning innovation and staff development (Balanza, 2018). These findings underscore the importance of allocating resources strategically to support the effective integration of Education 4.0 principles across all dimensions of instructional leadership, ultimately enhancing the quality of education and preparing students for success in the digital age.

Part IV. Challenges Experienced by the School Heads in Integrating Education 4.0 in their Instructional Leadership Practices

In Table 12, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 4, "Accessing high-quality digital educational content and tools." The mean score of 4.04 suggests that respondents perceive this challenge as particularly significant. This indicates that school heads encounter considerable difficulty in accessing digital educational resources that not only align with the curriculum but also cater to the diverse needs of students. The high mean score highlights the critical importance of having access to relevant and high-quality digital content and tools for the effective implementation of Education 4.0 initiatives. Without access to such resources, educators may struggle to engage students effectively and provide enriching learning experiences tailored to individual needs.

Table 12. *Weighted Mean of the School Heads on the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Availability of Resources*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Ensuring access to adequate technological infrastructure, including reliable internet connectivity and appropriate devices, poses a challenge, particularly in remote or underprivileged areas.	25	3.88	0.78	Much Challenged
2. Securing funding for the implementation and maintenance of digital tools, software licenses, and hardware upgrades can be challenging, especially for schools with limited budgets.	25	3.80	0.87	Much Challenged
3. Providing sufficient training and ongoing support for educators to effectively integrate technology into teaching practices requires dedicated resources, including time and financial investment.	25	3.84	0.90	Much Challenged
4. Accessing high-quality digital educational content and tools that align with the curriculum and meet the diverse needs of students can be challenging, particularly with the proliferation of options and varying costs.	25	4.04	0.84	Much Challenged
5. Ensuring equitable access to resources for all students, regardless of socioeconomic background or geographic location, remains a significant challenge, exacerbating existing disparities in educational opportunities.	25	3.88	0.78	Much Challenged
Composite Mean	25	3.89	0.83	Much Challenged

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 2, "Securing funding for the implementation and maintenance of digital tools, software licenses, and hardware upgrades." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed challenges, the mean score of 3.80 still indicates that respondents perceive funding as a notable challenge. This suggests that while securing funding may not be the most pressing concern compared to other challenges listed, it remains a significant obstacle in implementing Education 4.0 initiatives. Insufficient funding can hinder schools, particularly those with limited budgets, from acquiring and maintaining essential digital tools and resources for integrating Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership practices. Thus, addressing funding challenges remains crucial to ensuring equitable access to resources and promoting effective integration of Education 4.0 in schools.

It underscores the complex landscape of resource availability and distribution in the integration of Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices (Al-Kadri et al., 2020). These findings emphasize the importance of addressing these challenges to ensure equitable access to educational opportunities and effective implementation of Education 4.0 initiatives.

In Table 13, the mean score is associated with Statement 1, "School leaders often face challenges in balancing administrative responsibilities with their role in providing instructional leadership, particularly in the context of Education 4.0, which requires a greater focus on innovation and technology integration." The mean score of 3.92 indicates that respondents perceive this challenge as particularly significant. This suggests that school heads encounter considerable difficulty in managing their time effectively to balance administrative duties with the imperative to provide instructional leadership in the context of Education 4.0. The high mean score underscores the critical importance of time management skills for school leaders, especially as they navigate the demands of integrating innovative technologies and pedagogical approaches into their educational practices.

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 4, "Facilitating collaboration among teachers, staff, and external partners for initiatives such as project-based learning or interdisciplinary projects requires effective time management to coordinate schedules, meetings, and collaborative activities." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed challenges, the mean score of 3.76, still indicates that respondents perceive time management in collaboration facilitation as a notable challenge. This suggests that while coordinating collaborative efforts may not be the most pressing concern compared to other challenges listed, it remains a significant obstacle in the context of Education 4.0 leadership. Effective collaboration among stakeholders is essential for the successful

implementation of Education 4.0 initiatives, and challenges in time management could impede these efforts.

Table 13. *Weighted Mean of the School Heads on the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Time Management*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. School leaders often face challenges in balancing administrative responsibilities with their role in providing instructional leadership, particularly in the context of Education 4.0, which requires a greater focus on innovation and technology integration.	25	3.92	0.76	Much Challenged
2. Allocating sufficient time for professional development activities, such as training sessions on new technologies and pedagogical approaches, can be challenging amidst busy schedules and competing priorities.	25	3.88	0.93	Much Challenged
3. Keeping pace with rapid advancements in technology and educational trends requires school leaders to invest time in research, learning, and staying updated, which can be challenging given time constraints and the need to address immediate operational demands.	25	3.92	0.81	Much Challenged
4. Facilitating collaboration among teachers, staff, and external partners for initiatives such as project-based learning or interdisciplinary projects requires effective time management to coordinate schedules, meetings, and collaborative activities.	25	3.76	0.88	Much Challenged
5. School leaders may struggle to maintain a healthy work-life balance amidst the demands of Education 4.0 leadership, which may involve long hours, evening commitments, and the pressure to constantly innovate and improve educational practices.	25	3.84	0.94	Much Challenged
Composite Mean	25	3.86	0.86	Much Challenged

It highlights the critical role of time management in addressing challenges encountered by school leaders in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices. Balancing administrative responsibilities with instructional leadership roles and effectively coordinating collaborative efforts are vital areas where improved time management skills are crucial (Boje & Frederiksen, 2018). Enhancing time management strategies can enable school leaders to navigate the complexities of Education 4.0 leadership more effectively, ultimately contributing to the successful implementation of innovative educational practices.

In Table 14, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 5, "Schools often compete for limited funding sources, including government grants, private donations, and community support, making it challenging to secure adequate resources for Education 4.0 initiatives amidst competing priorities in education." The mean score of 4.00 indicates that respondents perceive this challenge as particularly significant. This suggests that school heads encounter considerable difficulty in securing adequate funding for Education 4.0 initiatives due to the competitive nature of funding sources and the presence of other competing priorities in education. The high mean score underscores the critical importance of financial matters in the successful implementation and sustainability of Education 4.0 programs.

Table 14. *Weighted Mean of the School Heads on the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Financial Matters*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Implementing Education 4.0 initiatives often requires significant initial investment in technology infrastructure, software licenses, digital tools, and training programs, which can strain school budgets.	25	3.80	0.91	Much Challenged
2. Sustaining Education 4.0 programs entails ongoing costs for maintenance, updates, technical support, and renewal of licenses, placing continued financial pressure on schools.	25	3.84	0.80	Much Challenged
3. Ensuring equitable access to technology and digital resources for all students regardless of socioeconomic background may require additional funding to provide devices, internet connectivity, and support services to underserved populations.	25	3.92	0.76	Much Challenged
4. Providing comprehensive training and professional development opportunities for educators to effectively integrate technology into teaching practices requires financial resources for workshops, seminars, and online courses.	25	3.80	0.76	Much Challenged
5. Schools often compete for limited funding sources, including government grants, private donations, and community support, making it challenging to secure adequate resources for Education 4.0 initiatives amidst competing priorities in education.	25	4.00	0.82	Much Challenged
Composite Mean	25	3.87	0.81	Much Challenged

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 1, "Implementing Education 4.0 initiatives often requires significant initial investment in technology infrastructure, software licenses, digital tools, and training programs, which can strain school budgets." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed challenges, the mean score of 3.80 still indicates that respondents perceive financial strain from initial investment as a notable challenge. This suggests that while initial investment challenges may not be the most pressing concern compared to other financial matters listed, they remain a significant obstacle in implementing Education 4.0 initiatives. Insufficient initial investment can hinder the adoption of necessary technologies and training programs required for the effective integration of Education 4.0 principles.

It highlights the critical role of financial matters in addressing challenges encountered by school heads in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices. Securing adequate funding and managing financial resources effectively are essential for the successful implementation and sustainability of Education 4.0 initiatives (Jones & Sharma, 2021). Additionally, addressing the challenges associated with competing for limited funding sources is crucial to ensuring equitable access to technology and digital resources for all students, regardless of socioeconomic background (Kumar, 2017).

In Table 15, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 4, "Limited resources, including time, funding, and personnel, may impede stakeholders' ability to actively participate in Education 4.0 initiatives, limiting their capacity to provide meaningful support and collaboration." The mean score of 4.04 indicates that respondents perceive resource constraints as a particularly significant challenge. This suggests that stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and community members, face considerable difficulty in actively participating in Education 4.0 initiatives due to limitations in time, funding, and personnel. The high mean score underscores the critical importance of resource allocation and support mechanisms for enabling stakeholders to engage effectively in Education 4.0 initiatives.

Table 15. *Weighted Mean of the School Heads on the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Support from Stakeholders*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Some stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and community members, may resist adopting Education 4.0 practices due to fear of technology, lack of familiarity, or concerns about the impact on traditional teaching methods.	25	3.92	0.91	Much Challenged
2. Stakeholders may lack awareness or understanding of the benefits of Education 4.0, leading to skepticism or reluctance to support initiatives without clear communication and engagement strategies.	25	3.96	0.89	Much Challenged
3. Stakeholders, particularly teachers and school administrators, may lack the necessary training and support to effectively implement Education 4.0 practices, hindering their ability to fully embrace and advocate for the approach.	25	3.88	0.78	Much Challenged
4. Limited resources, including time, funding, and personnel, may impede stakeholders' ability to actively participate in Education 4.0 initiatives, limiting their capacity to provide meaningful support and collaboration.	25	4.04	0.89	Much Challenged
5. Stakeholders may have conflicting priorities, interests, and agendas that make it challenging to align efforts and collaborate effectively on Education 4.0 initiatives, requiring careful negotiation and consensus-building strategies.	25	3.88	0.78	Much Challenged
Composite Mean	25	3.94	0.85	Much Challenged

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 3, "Stakeholders, particularly teachers and school administrators, may lack the necessary training and support to effectively implement Education 4.0 practices, hindering their ability to fully embrace and advocate for the approach." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed challenges, the mean score of 3.88 still indicates that respondents perceive a lack of training and support as a notable challenge. This suggests that while training and support issues may not be the most pressing concern compared to other challenges listed, they remain a significant obstacle in fully embracing and advocating for Education 4.0 practices. Insufficient training and support can hinder stakeholders' ability to effectively implement and advocate for Education 4.0 approaches.

It highlights the critical role of support from stakeholders in addressing challenges encountered by school heads in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices. Adequate resources, including time, funding, and personnel, are essential for enabling stakeholders to actively participate in Education 4.0 initiatives and provide meaningful support and collaboration (Jensen, 2020). Additionally, providing necessary training and support to stakeholders is crucial for enhancing their capacity to implement and advocate for Education 4.0 practices effectively. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering a collaborative and supportive environment conducive to the successful integration of Education 4.0 principles in schools (Eller & Eller, 2018).

Table 16 displays the consolidated results of the challenges encountered by the school head in integrating Education 4.0. As displayed in the table, support from the stakeholders has the highest composite mean of 3.94 followed by availability of resources with 3.89; financial matters have a mean of 3.87, and time management is 3.86. All these areas fall under much-challenged level, which means

that they are encountered by the school head within 75% to 99% frequency.

Table 16. *Summary of the Weighted Mean of the School Heads on the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices*

<i>Areas of Integration</i>	<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Availability of Resources	3.89	Much Challenged
Time Management	3.86	Much Challenged
Financial Matters	3.87	Much Challenged
Support from Stakeholders	3.94	Much Challenged
Grand Mean	3.89	Much Challenged

Regarding the challenges encountered with support from stakeholders, it indicates that school heads receive minimal assistance from the school's stakeholders, which include parents, the local government unit of the town and barangay, the business sector, and other community members, all of whom play vital roles in initiating projects and enhancing school infrastructure. Resources are also a concern because, in Education 4.0, the primary resources needed are information communication and technology equipment, typically provided by the DepEd Central Office, leading to scarcity in many schools. Additionally, the ratio of ICT equipment to classes is typically only one set per school. School heads also face financial challenges since Education 4.0 demands technologically advanced materials and tools, requiring funds beyond what is typically allocated in public school budgets, which primarily cover maintenance and other operating expenses (MOOE) monthly. However, these funds are often insufficient to cover all expenses, including purchasing ICT equipment.

This situation implies that school heads need to be more resourceful in finding solutions to the challenges encountered in integrating Education 4.0 into their instructional leadership practices. They are advised to establish strong connections within the community to identify potential sources of funding. To achieve this, they must earn the trust of these individuals and even the teachers. Additionally, there should be a designated fund for ICT equipment maintenance and purchase, even a small percentage of the budget allocated monthly could make a significant difference for the entire school. In the face of resource scarcity, they should implement programs aimed at addressing this problem.

Part V. Coping Strategies Employed by the School Head to Address the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices

In Table 17, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 5, "Implementing mobile tech initiatives for fair access, leveraging community and government support." The mean score of 4.16 indicates that respondents perceive this coping strategy as particularly effective. This suggests that school heads find implementing mobile technology initiatives, with support from the community and government, to be a highly beneficial approach for ensuring fair access to technology resources. The high mean score underscores the perceived effectiveness of leveraging mobile technology to bridge the digital divide and provide equitable access to digital tools and resources for all students, regardless of socioeconomic background or geographic location.

Table 17. *Weighted Mean of the Coping Strategies Employed by the School Head to Address the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Availability of Resources*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Collaborate with tech companies and NGOs for discounted or donated tech resources.	25	3.92	0.81	Sometimes Employed
2. Invest in grant writing and fundraising efforts to secure funding for digital tools.	25	3.84	0.75	Sometimes Employed
3. Develop professional development programs for educators to integrate tech effectively.	25	3.88	0.78	Sometimes Employed
4. Use OER to access quality digital content at low or no cost.	25	3.92	0.81	Sometimes Employed
5. Implement mobile tech initiatives for fair access, leveraging community and government support.	25	4.16	0.69	Sometimes Employed
Composite Mean	25	3.94	0.77	Sometimes Employed

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 2, "Invest in grant writing and fundraising efforts to secure funding for digital tools." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed coping strategies, the mean score of 3.84 still indicates that respondents perceive grant writing and fundraising efforts as a relatively effective strategy. This suggests that while investing in grant writing and fundraising may not be perceived as the most effective coping strategy compared to others listed, it remains a valuable approach for securing funding for digital tools. The relatively lower mean score may reflect the challenges and uncertainties associated with grant writing and fundraising efforts, as well as the competitive nature of securing funding.

The various coping strategies employed by school heads to address challenges encountered in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices, particularly concerning the availability of resources, are varied. Implementing mobile technology initiatives with community and government support emerges as a highly effective strategy for ensuring fair access to technology resources (Lacuna et al., 2020). However, investing in grant writing and fundraising efforts remain a valuable approach for securing

funding for digital tools, despite being perceived as relatively less effective compared to other strategies. These coping strategies play a crucial role in overcoming resource constraints and promoting the successful integration of Education 4.0 principles in schools (Jones & Sharma, 2021).

In Table 18, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 1, "School leaders can delegate administrative responsibilities to trusted staff members or administrative teams, allowing them to focus more on instructional leadership tasks related to Education 4.0." The mean score of 4.16 indicates that respondents perceive this coping strategy as particularly effective in addressing challenges related to time management. This suggests that delegating administrative tasks to trusted staff members or teams is seen as an effective way for school leaders to allocate more time and focus on instructional leadership tasks, specifically those related to integrating Education 4.0 principles. The high mean score underscores the importance of delegation in optimizing time management and prioritizing instructional leadership responsibilities amidst administrative demand.

Table 18. *Weighted Mean of the Coping Strategies Employed by the School Head to Address the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Time Management*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. School leaders can delegate administrative responsibilities to trusted staff members or administrative teams, allowing them to focus more on instructional leadership tasks related to Education 4.0.	25	4.16	0.75	Sometimes Employed
2. Allocate regular time slots specifically for professional development activities, ensuring that training sessions on new technologies and pedagogical approaches are prioritized and consistently attended.	25	3.80	0.91	Sometimes Employed
3. Take advantage of online platforms, webinars, and professional networks to stay updated on technology advancements and educational trends, allowing school leaders to engage in learning and research at their own pace and convenience.	25	3.80	0.87	Sometimes Employed
4. Establish clear communication channels and protocols to facilitate collaboration among teachers, staff, and external partners, making it easier to coordinate schedules, meetings, and collaborative activities for initiatives like project-based learning.	25	3.76	0.88	Sometimes Employed
5. Encourage school leaders to set boundaries between work and personal life, scheduling regular breaks and prioritizing self-care activities to maintain a healthy work-life balance. Encourage delegation and effective time management to reduce the pressure of constantly innovating and improving educational practices.	25	3.80	0.91	Sometimes Employed
Composite Mean	25	3.86	0.86	Sometimes Employed

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 4, "Establish clear communication channels and protocols to facilitate collaboration among teachers, staff, and external partners, making it easier to coordinate schedules, meetings, and collaborative activities for initiatives like project-based learning." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed coping strategies, the mean score of 3.76 still indicates that respondents perceive establishing clear communication channels as a relatively effective strategy. This suggests that while clear communication channels may not be perceived as the most effective coping strategy compared to others listed, they remain a valuable approach for facilitating collaboration and coordination among stakeholders. The relatively lower mean score may reflect the challenges associated with establishing effective communication channels and protocols.

The various coping strategies employed by school heads to address challenges encountered in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices, particularly concerning time management. Delegating administrative responsibilities emerge as a highly effective strategy for optimizing time management and prioritizing instructional leadership tasks (Jensen, 2020). However, establishing clear communication channels remains a valuable approach to facilitating collaboration and coordination among stakeholders despite being perceived as relatively less effective compared to other strategies (Pasia, 2019). These coping strategies play a crucial role in enabling school leaders to effectively manage their time and address the demands of integrating Education 4.0 principles in schools.

In Table 19, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 3, "Research and implement cost-effective alternatives for technology infrastructure and digital tools, such as open-source software, refurbished devices, and shared resources with other schools or institutions." The mean score of 3.96 indicates that respondents perceive this coping strategy as particularly effective in addressing challenges related to financial matters. This suggests that researching and implementing cost-effective alternatives for technology infrastructure and digital tools are seen as effective ways for school heads to mitigate financial constraints associated with Education 4.0 initiatives. The high mean score underscores the importance of exploring innovative and resource-efficient solutions to support the integration of Education 4.0 principles within limited budgets.

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 1, "School leaders can actively pursue external sources of funding such as government grants, corporate sponsorships, and community partnerships to supplement school budgets and finance Education 4.0

initiatives." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed coping strategies, the mean score of 3.72 still indicates that respondents perceive pursuing external sources of funding as a relatively effective strategy. This suggests that while actively pursuing external funding sources may not be perceived as the most effective coping strategy compared to others listed, it remains a valuable approach for supplementing school budgets and financing Education 4.0 initiatives. Relatively lower mean score may reflect the challenges and uncertainties associated with securing external funding sources.

Table 19. *Weighted Mean of the Coping Strategies Employed by the School Head to Address the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices as to Financial Matters*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. School leaders can actively pursue external sources of funding such as government grants, corporate sponsorships, and community partnerships to supplement school budgets and finance Education 4.0 initiatives.	25	3.72	0.94	Sometimes Employed
2. Allocate existing resources strategically, prioritizing investments in technology infrastructure and professional development programs that directly support Education 4.0 goals and sustainability.	25	3.80	0.65	Sometimes Employed
3. Research and implement cost-effective alternatives for technology infrastructure and digital tools, such as open-source software, refurbished devices, and shared resources with other schools or institutions.	25	3.96	0.79	Sometimes Employed
4. Collaborate with local businesses, technology companies, and nonprofit organizations to establish partnerships that provide access to discounted or donated technology resources, training programs, and support services.	25	3.92	0.76	Sometimes Employed
5. Advocate for increased funding and resources for Education 4.0 initiatives at the local, regional, and national levels, highlighting the importance of equitable access technology and digital resources for all students in today's digital age.	25	3.84	0.80	Sometimes Employed
Composite Mean	25	3.85	0.79	Sometimes Employed

It highlights various coping strategies employed by school heads to address challenges encountered in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices, particularly concerning financial matters. Researching and implementing cost-effective alternatives emerge as a highly effective strategy for mitigating financial constraints and supporting Education 4.0 initiatives within limited budgets (Leithwood et al., 2017). However, actively pursuing external sources of funding remains a valuable approach for supplementing school budgets despite being perceived as relatively less effective compared to other strategies (Ma et al., 2019). These coping strategies play a crucial role in enabling school leaders to overcome financial challenges and promote the successful integration of Education 4.0 principles in schools.

In Table 20, the highest mean score is associated with Statement 1, "Provide comprehensive training and ongoing support to stakeholders, building their confidence in Education 4.0." The mean score of 3.8 indicates that respondents perceive this coping strategy as relatively effective in addressing challenges related to support from stakeholders. This suggests that providing comprehensive training and ongoing support to stakeholders is seen as an essential approach to building their confidence and capacity in adopting Education 4.0 practices. The relatively high mean score underscores the significance of investing in the professional development of stakeholders to ensure their readiness and commitment to embracing Education 4.0 principles.

Table 20. *Weighted Mean of the Coping Strategies Employed by the School Head to Address the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices to Support from Stakeholders*

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. Provide comprehensive training and ongoing support to stakeholders, building their confidence in Education 4.0.	25	3.8	0.87	Sometimes Employed
2. Develop compelling communication strategies to highlight the benefits of Education 4.0.	25	3.64	1.00	Sometimes Employed
3. Foster collaboration among stakeholders through professional learning communities.	25	3.72	1.06	Sometimes Employed
4. Utilize online platforms and virtual meetings to overcome resource limitations.	25	3.68	1.11	Sometimes Employed
5. Involve stakeholders in decision-making processes to address concerns and ensure buy-in.	25	3.72	1.06	Sometimes Employed
Composite Mean	25	3.71	1.02	Sometimes Employed

Conversely, the lowest mean score is linked to Statement 2, "Develop compelling communication strategies to highlight the benefits of Education 4.0." Despite being the lowest mean score among the listed coping strategies, the mean score of 3.64 still indicates that respondents perceive developing compelling communication strategies as a moderately effective approach. This suggests that while developing communication strategies to highlight the benefits of Education 4.0 may not be perceived as the most effective strategy

compared to others listed, it remains an important aspect of garnering support from stakeholders. The relatively lower mean score may reflect the challenges associated with crafting and implementing communication strategies that effectively convey the benefits of Education 4.0 to diverse stakeholders.

These highlight various coping strategies employed by school heads to address challenges encountered in integrating Education 4.0 into instructional leadership practices, particularly concerning support from stakeholders. Providing comprehensive training and ongoing support is a relatively effective strategy for building stakeholders' confidence in Education 4.0 (Pasia, 2019). However, developing compelling communication strategies remains an essential aspect of garnering support from stakeholders, despite being perceived as relatively less effective compared to other strategies (Vogel, 2018). These coping strategies play a crucial role in fostering stakeholder engagement and commitment to the successful integration of Education 4.0 principles in schools.

Table 21 presents the consolidated results of how the school heads cope with the challenges they have faced in line with the integration of Education 4.0. As presented in the table, the availability of resources has the highest composite mean of 3.94, followed by time management with 3.86, financial matters with 3.85, and the last is support from stakeholders with 3.71 in which all those values are verbally interpreted as sometimes applied.

Table 21. Summary of Results of the Coping Strategies Employed by the School Head to Address the Challenges Encountered in Integrating Education 4.0 in Instructional Leadership Practices to Support from Stakeholders

Statements	Composite Mean	Interpretation
1. Availability of Resources	3.94	Sometimes Employed
2. Time Management	3.86	Sometimes Employed
3. Financial Matters	3.85	Sometimes Employed
4. Support from Stakeholders	3.71	Sometimes Employed
Grand Mean	3.84	Sometimes Employed

The coping mechanisms included in availability of resources are the highest coping strategies employed by the school heads because they have direct contact or mostly needed in practicing instructional leadership. So, school head must put it on their priority to solve problems regarding scarcity of resources to ensure effective integration of Education 4.0 and effective delivery of instruction in general. School heads also focused on managing time because it is needed especially if there are lots of overlapping activities that are required to accomplish in a certain period of time. So, school heads should manage time well so that all activities are done effectively.

Part VI. Development Plan Formulated Based on the Results of the Study That Will Help the School Head to be Prepared for Education 5.0

To effectively prepare school heads for the transition to Education 5.0, a comprehensive development plan must be formulated based on the study's findings. The plan includes key components derived from identified challenges and coping strategies. Firstly, a robust professional development program will be established, offering tailored training sessions and workshops to equip educators with skills necessary for integrating emerging technologies and personalized learning approaches inherent in Education 5.0. Concurrently, a stakeholder engagement and communication strategy will be devised to foster understanding and garner support for Education 5.0 initiatives among teachers, parents, students, and the wider community, ensuring transparency and collaboration in decision-making processes.

Strategic resource allocation will prioritize directing funds towards technology infrastructure, professional development, and innovative teaching resources aligned with Education 5.0 principles. Collaborative partnerships with external entities, such as technology firms and NGOs, will be cultivated to access additional resources and expertise, further supporting Education 5.0 implementation. Moreover, support mechanisms for time management and work-life balance will be implemented to mitigate potential burnout among school heads, promoting delegation and self-care practices for sustained effective leadership.

The development plan will emphasize a culture of continuous learning and innovation within the school community, encouraging educators to experiment, reflect, and collaborate on refining teaching practices aligned with Education 5.0 goals. Additionally, mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of Education 5.0 initiatives will be established to enable data-informed decision-making and iterative improvements. Implementing this comprehensive development plan will better equip school heads to navigate the transition to Education 5.0, ensuring readiness to embrace emerging technologies and personalized learning approaches to meet the evolving needs of future learners.

Conclusion

Based on the study findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

School heads in Mulanay Districts 1 and 2 actively integrate Education 4.0 principles into instructional leadership, displaying a commitment to innovation and technology integration.

Despite challenges like resource constraints and time management, school heads employ coping strategies, showcasing adaptability

and resilience in Education 4.0 integration.

Significant differences in Education 4.0 integration exist based on demographic factors like school size and allocated budget, suggesting the need for tailored approaches.

Financial challenges and stakeholder support are key areas requiring attention, emphasizing the importance of partnerships and increased funding.

The development plan, based on study findings, emphasizes ongoing professional development, partnerships, and strategic resource allocation to prepare for Education 5.0.

Overall, the study highlights the critical role of school leadership in Education 4.0 integration, guiding informed decision-making and strategic planning for future educational paradigms.

Considering the study's conclusions, the following recommendations are recommended:

For DepEd School Division Office (SDO) Officials: Prioritize strategic resource allocation and policy support to facilitate seamless Education 4.0 integration. Provide funding and tailored professional development for school heads and teachers. Foster partnerships with stakeholders to supplement resources and offer ongoing guidance to school leaders.

For school heads: Prioritize professional development and foster innovation within schools. Engage in continuous learning and advocate for adequate resource allocation. Encourage staff collaboration and advocate for supportive school policies and partnerships.

For teachers: Participate in professional development to enhance digital literacy and pedagogical approaches aligned with Education 4.0. Embrace a growth mindset, collaborate with colleagues, and promote dynamic learning environments for students.

For pupils: Foster positive attitudes towards technology and promote digital literacy skills. Encourage engagement with technology and provide access to diverse digital tools. Emphasize ethical use while instilling digital citizenship and online safety values.

For researchers: Utilize the findings to inform future research on Education 4.0 integration. Explore contextual factors influencing the implementation and efficacy of coping strategies. Collaborate to conduct longitudinal studies assessing the impact on student learning outcomes, teacher development, and school performance.

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